

Data-constrained AI optimization of solketal–gasoline blends for low emission engine operation

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Abstract

Solketal, a glycerol-derived oxygenate, is a promising gasoline blending component for reducing spark-ignition exhaust pollutants, but identifying practical operating points requires navigating multi-variable tradeoffs under limited test data. This study develops a data-constrained, surrogate-assisted multi-objective optimization workflow using a 90-point full-factorial experimental matrix on a spark-ignition generator, spanning electrical load (400–2000 W), solketal fraction (0–20% v/v), and gasoline octane (88, 91, 95 RON). XGBoost surrogate models are embedded within NSGA-III to search for non-dominated operating points while explicitly restricting the search to data-supported regions using a convex-hull feasibility filter and a trust-region proximity constraint. From the constrained Pareto set, an achievement-scalarizing compromise was selected at 1627.86 W, 8.19% solketal, and ~88 RON. At this point, the surrogate predicts NO_x = 19.64 ppm and HC = 166.94 ppm. Relative to a gasoline-only baseline evaluated at the same load and octane, the values were: NO_x = 20.59 ppm, HC = 200.27 ppm. This corresponds to reductions of 4.6% in NO_x and 16.6% in HC, demonstrating that feasibility-constrained surrogate optimization can generate emissions-favorable solketal–gasoline recommendations while limiting extrapolation risk under data scarcity.

Keywords: Solketal–gasoline blends; Spark-ignition generator; XGBoost surrogate modeling; Data-constrained optimization; NSGA-III; Low Emission Engines; Sustainable Development Goals

1 Introduction

The world energy situation is now facing a revolutionary change as the auto industry and the power generation industry contend with challenges of rising energy demand and strict environmental policies. Although the world is gradually moving towards all electrification, internal combustion engines (ICEs) still form a backbone of world infrastructure, especially in decentralized power generation [1, 2]. The ongoing use of the spark-ignition (SI) technology also demands a parallel evolution in the fuel chemistry and fuel management tactics to mitigate the environmental footprint

of conventional fuel made of petroleum. Hereby, the quest to achieve cleaner combustion is not just an engineering urge anymore but a worldwide requirement in line with the world sustainability objectives[3, 4].

The introduction of oxygenated biofuels into the gasoline pool has become one of the most possible directions of a quick cut in carbon intensity. Oxygenates, which are highly oxygenated and have good octane-enhancing properties, undergo a greater complete combustion process, thus reducing the formation of such criteria pollutants as carbon monoxide and unburned hydrocarbons. Although the adoption of first-generation biofuels such as ethanol has been wide spread, it has been criticized on its competition with food supplies, as well as its effect on land use. This has refocused science on so-called second generation or even so-called waste-to-fuel routes, in which feedstocks no longer come from food crops but instead as industrial byproducts.

Glycerol, one of the main byproducts of the process of biodiesel production, is an enormous prospect in this circular bioeconomy. With the production of biodiesel in the world having climbed to renewable energy levels, a huge quantity of crude glycerol has been generated, which is usually far surpassing the demand rates of the traditional uses of the glycerol in pharmaceutical and cosmetic sectors. This excess has led to the establishment of glycerol-based oxygenates, the best of which is solketal (4-hydroxymethyl-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxolane). Solketal has a number of benefits as a gasoline blending compound[5, 6]. It is quite highly miscible with hydrocarbons, increases fuel stability, and is a useful oxygen carrier that can considerably change the combustion chemistry in the cylinder to favor lower tailpipe emissions.

Non-linear interactions however arise with the advent of a new oxygenate in a sophisticated engine setting, which is not so easily predicted by chemical theory. The operation of a fuel blend does not solely depend on its chemical structure but largely depends on the operating conditions of an engine, including electrical load, ignition timing and the basic octane quality of the gasoline itself[7, 8]. The engines can often be loaded at different levels, and the compromise between the Brake Thermal Efficiency (BTE) and the controlled emissions such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and the unburned hydrocarbons (HC) is often a major technical challenge.

In the past, the engine-fuel co-optimization process used to be by relying on numerous trial and error experimental campaigns[9, 10]. Although strict, this method is becoming unsustainable because of the high cost of special fuels and time to complete mapping in multidimensional realms of factors. Moreover, the very nature of the tradeoff between efficiency and emissions can cause a moving target to the engineers; a point that maximizes power can cause a spike in NO_x, and an emissions-optimal point may hurt fuel economy. This poses a multi-objective problem in which there is no single perfect answer, but a series of tradeoffs that one needs to tread cautiously[11, 12].

To address these complexities, the contemporary research paradigm is moving towards the combination of experimental facts and the sophisticated systems of calculations[13, 14]. It is the possibility to simulate complex, multi-variable, and combustion process dynamics in high-fidelity surrogates that enables a more fine-grained interpretation of fuel chemistry-mechanical load interactions. Having seen fuel-engine optimization in the perspective of data science, the

researchers can go beyond mere observation and start tracing on the diagram of the conflict structure of the system[15, 16]. This would facilitate the determination of operating regions that would meet performance demands as well as environmental limitations, so that the implementation of sustainable fuel such as solketal is not achieved to the cost of operational reliability and efficiency.

The objectives of this study are to identify an operating region that reduces emissions in solketal–gasoline SI operation, to quantify the emissions benefit of the selected compromise point relative to a matched gasoline baseline, and to validate the robustness of the recommended settings by comparing the NSGA-III compromise solution against the baseline (0% solketal / 100% gasoline) and the RSM desirability optimum.

2 Methods and Computational Workflow

2.1 Engine test platform and measurements

2.1.1 Engine generator unit

Experiments were conducted on a Honda EZ3000X generator driven by a Honda GP200 spark ignition engine. The engine is a single cylinder, four stroke, air cooled unit with an overhead valve train and a carbureted fuel delivery system. The displacement is 196 cm³ and the compression ratio is 8.5:1. Ignition is a transistorized magneto, and the engine uses recoil starting. The generator rated AC output is 2.3 kVA with a maximum of 2.5 kVA. Key engine and generator specifications are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Engine generator specifications

Item	Specification
Engine-generator unit	Honda EZ3000X generator with Honda GP200 engine
Engine type	Single-cylinder, four-stroke, OHV, air-cooled, spark-ignition
Fuel delivery	Carburetor
Displacement	196 cm ³
Compression ratio	8.5:1
Ignition system	Transistorized magneto
Starting method	Recoil start
Generator rated AC output	2.3 kVA
Generator maximum AC output	2.5 kVA
Peak torque range	20.0–24.0 N·m

2.1.2 Electrical loading and power verification

Engine loading was implemented using external resistive loads. Five discrete electrical load conditions were applied: 400 W, 800 W, 1200 W, 1600 W, and 2000 W. Electrical power was verified using inline wattmeter and multimeter measurements. The data acquisition setup included a PZM-004T power meter module integrated into the measurement chain. The experimental and measurement layout and the engine to design matrix pipeline are provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Experimental hardware and engine to design matrix pipeline (engine and measurements through DOE dataset creation)

2.1.3 Exhaust emissions recording

Exhaust gas measurements were recorded for CO, CO₂, HC, NO_x, SO₂, and O₂ using an automotive exhaust gas analyzer. The instrument was calibrated before each experimental session. Although multiple exhaust species were recorded, this study uses only NO_x and HC as optimization targets to match the multi objective formulation.

2.1.4 Fuel consumption measurement and reported responses

Fuel consumption was measured by timing the consumption of a fixed fuel volume of 100 mL using calibrated laboratory glassware and a stopwatch. Brake thermal efficiency (BTE) values used for modeling and optimization were taken from the processed experimental dataset associated with

each operating point, together with the measured NO_x and HC values. The final responses used in this study are:

- BTE (%)
- NO_x (ppm)
- HC (ppm)

2.2 Fuels and experimental design matrix

2.2.1 Base gasoline and octane definition

Three gasoline categories were tested, corresponding to research octane number (RON) values of 88, 91, and 95. In the dataset, octane number is stored numerically and used as a factor in both surrogate modeling and optimization.

2.2.1.1 Solketal blend levels

Solketal (4-hydroxymethyl-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxolane) was blended volumetrically with gasoline at five blend levels: 4%, 8%, 12%, 16%, and 20% (v/v). Pure gasoline (0% solketal) was also tested for each octane category to provide baseline reference points.

2.2.1.2 Factor levels and dataset size

The experimental design was defined by three controlled factors: electrical load, solketal volumetric fraction, and gasoline octane number. Electrical load was evaluated at five discrete levels from 400 to 2000 W. Solketal content was evaluated at six levels including the gasoline baseline (0, 4, 8, 12, 16, and 20% v/v). Three gasoline types were considered, corresponding to octane numbers of 88, 91, and 95 RON. The resulting design comprised 90 operating points in total, including 75 solketal blend points formed by combining five nonzero solketal levels with three octane levels and five load levels, and 15 baseline gasoline points formed by combining 0% solketal with the same three octane levels and five load levels. The details for experimental factor levels are mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2: Experimental factor levels and number of operating points

Factor	Levels	Units	Notes
Electrical load	400, 800, 1200, 1600, 2000	W	Load applied using resistive electrical loads and verified using power measurement instrumentation
Solketal content	0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20	% v/v	0% corresponds to the gasoline-only baseline
Octane number	88, 91, 95	RON	Three gasoline types corresponding to low, medium, and high-octane categories
Total operating points	90	–	75 blend points (4–20% solketal × 3 octane × 5 load) plus 15 baseline points (0% solketal × 3 octane × 5 load)

2.3 Dataset assembly and feature processing

2.3.1.1 Interaction feature and scaling

To capture pairwise coupling effects among the three experimental factors, three interaction features were added: Load \times Solketal, Load \times Octane, and Solketal \times Octane. The surrogate input vector therefore contained six features: [Load, Solketal, Octane, Load \times Solketal, Load \times Octane, Solketal \times Octane].

All input features were standardized using Z-score scaling (StandardScaler) fitted on the training subset and applied to the test subset. The same scaling pipeline was also used during NSGA-III evaluation when computing the trust-region proximity constraint.

2.4 XGBoost surrogate model construction

2.4.1 Train test split and cross validation

Three independent eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) regression models were trained, one for each response. The dataset was split using an 80/20 partition, yielding 72 training samples and 18 test samples. Within the training subset, a 5-fold KFold procedure was used. Hyperparameter selection was performed using GridSearchCV with the scoring function set to negative root mean squared error.

2.4.2 Hyperparameter search space and final settings

Hyperparameter tuning for each surrogate was performed using GridSearchCV with five-fold cross-validation and a negative RMSE scoring function. The grid search explored combinations of tree count, tree depth, learning rate, row subsampling, column subsampling, and regularization terms. The best cross-validated RMSE scores were -0.34469 for BTE, -1.97290 for NO_x, and -3.74834 for HC. The selected parameter sets differed by target, reflecting response-specific model complexity requirements, and the final tuned hyperparameters adopted for subsequent training and optimization are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Final XGBoost hyperparameters used per target model

Target	CV RMSE (neg)	N-estimators	Max Depth	Learning Rate	Sub-Sample	Cosample Bytree	Gamma	Min Child Weight	Reg alpha	Reg lambda
BTE (%)	-0.34469	1000	5	0.05	0.70	0.85	0.10	3	0.10	5.0
NO _x (ppm)	-1.97290	1000	3	0.05	0.85	0.85	0.10	3	0.10	5.0
HC (ppm)	-3.74834	1000	3	0.05	0.70	0.85	0.10	3	0.10	5.0

The tuned XGBoost hyperparameters control model capacity, learning dynamics, sampling randomness, and regularization. `n_estimators` sets how many boosting trees are built, while `learning_rate` scales each tree's contribution so the model learns gradually rather than making large jumps. `max_depth` limits how complex each tree can become (i.e., how many interaction levels it can represent). To improve generalization, `subsample` and `colsample_bytree` randomly sample rows and features for each tree, respectively, which reduces variance and helps prevent overfitting.

The remaining parameters act as split/complexity guards and weight penalties. `gamma` requires a minimum reduction in loss before allowing a split, making tree growth more conservative. `min_child_weight` prevents splits that would create very small, potentially noisy leaves. Finally, `reg_alpha` (L1) and `reg_lambda` (L2) regularizes leaf weights to discourage overly large or overly complex solutions, improving stability and predictive robustness across folds.

2.4.2.1 Surrogate evaluation metrics

Predictive accuracy was quantified using MAE, MSE, MAPE, and R2, computed on the held-out test subset for each target. Equations 1-4 give mathematical interpretation for the metrics used.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (1)$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (4)$$

2.5 Multi objective optimization with NSGA-III

Decision variables, bounds, and objective vector

NSGA-III was applied using three decision variables: Load (W), bounded by 400 to 2000 - Solketal (% v/v), bounded by 0 to 20 and Octane (RON), bounded by 88 to 95.

The objective vector was defined by Equation (5):

$$\min F(x) = [-BTE(x), NO_x(x), HC(x)] \quad (5)$$

where BTE, NO_x, and HC were evaluated using the trained XGBoost surrogate models. Octane was treated as a continuous variable in the optimizer because it is a numeric feature in the surrogate model. As a result, NSGA-III can return intermediate octane values within 88 to 95.

2.5.1.1 Convex hull feasibility filter

A convex hull constraint was constructed using Delaunay triangulation in the raw three-dimensional input space (load, solketal, and octane number). A candidate point was treated as feasible for this constraint only if it lies inside the triangulated domain formed by the experimental observations.

2.5.1.2 Trust region proximity constraint

A second constraint was used to enforce proximity to observed data. Candidate points were mapped into the standardized feature space that includes the interaction term, and the minimum Euclidean distance to the training set was computed. The trust region threshold was set to 0.95 and feasibility constraint is given by Equation (6):

$$d_{min}(x) - \tau \leq 0 \quad (6)$$

where $d_{min}(x)$ the minimum distance from candidate point (x) to any training point in the scaled feature space.

2.5.1.3 NSGA-III configuration and constraint handling

Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm –III (NSGA-III) optimization was conducted in the pymoo framework using a three-objective formulation ($M = 3$). Reference directions were generated using the Das–Dennis method with ($H = 16$), resulting in 153 directions and a matched population size of 153 individuals. The algorithm was executed for 1000 generations with a fixed random seed of 42. Simulated binary crossover and polynomial mutation were applied using the default operator settings provided by pymoo. The convex hull and trust region feasibility checks were implemented directly as inequality constraints through the pymoo constraint vector (G); consequently, feasibility was handled internally during constrained non-dominated sorting, rather than through an externally defined penalty constant. The exact configuration of the NSGA-III setup is illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4: NSGA-III configuration and constraint handling

Component	Setting
Number of objectives (M)	3
Reference direction method	Das–Dennis
Reference direction parameter (H)	16
Number of reference directions	153
Population size	153
Number of generations	1000
Random seed	42

Component	Setting
Crossover operator	Simulated binary crossover (SBX)
Mutation operator	Polynomial mutation (PM)
Constraint handling	Inequality constraints via pymoo constraint vector (G)
Feasibility enforcement	Constrained non-dominated sorting within NSGA-III

2.5.1.4 Knee point selection using ASF

A single compromise solution was selected from the final Pareto set using the achievement scalarizing function (ASF) with equal weights. The solution's final equation uses the ASF as shown in Equation (7)

$$x^* = [\min] ASF(F_i, w) \quad (7)$$

2.6 RSM desirability optimization for cross-check

2.6.1.1 Response surface model form

For an independent optimization baseline, the same experimental dataset was imported into Design-Expert. Quadratic polynomial response surfaces (second order) with interaction terms were fitted separately for BTE, NOx, and HC.

2.6.1.2 Desirability configuration and fixed octane surfaces

Desirability optimization was configured to maximize BTE while simultaneously minimizing Nox and HC, with load, solketal fraction, and octane number constrained to their respective experimental ranges. To support interpretation of the fitted response surfaces, 3D plots were generated at fixed octane settings representing the low- and high-octane cases, specifically 88 RON and 95 RON, respectively.

3 Results

3.1 Data matrix used for modeling and optimization

The final dataset comprised 90 complete operating points, and no observations were removed during cleaning because the required input and response fields contained no missing values. The 90 points correspond to the full factorial combination of the tested factor levels (load, solketal fraction, and octane category).

For surrogate modeling, each operating point was represented using six input features: three base variables (Load, Solketal, Octane) and three pairwise interaction terms (Load \times Solketal, Load \times Octane, Solketal \times Octane). The three modeled responses were BTE, NOx, and HC.

3.2 Predictive fidelity of XGBoost surrogates

Three independent XGBoost regression models were developed to predict BTE, NO_x, and HC from experimental inputs. The dataset was partitioned using an 80/20 holdout split with `random_state = 42`, yielding 72 training points and 18 test points. Prior to training, all input features were standardized using a `StandardScaler` fit on the training subset and then applied consistently to the test subset.

Table 5: XGBoost model accuracy on the training and test subsets

Target	Subset	R ²	RMSE	MSE	MAE	MAPE (%)
BTE (%)	Train	0.9949	0.2025	0.0410	0.1342	1.2172
BTE (%)	Test	0.9771	0.4389	0.1926	0.3035	2.8293
NO _x (ppm)	Train	0.9977	0.4536	0.2058	0.3182	1.6956
NO _x (ppm)	Test	0.9795	1.5747	2.4797	0.9456	6.1562
HC (ppm)	Train	0.9997	0.5551	0.3081	0.3870	0.1795
HC (ppm)	Test	0.9901	2.4437	5.9717	2.1293	0.9710

Figures 2a,3a, and 4a report learning curves as mean squared error versus boosting iterations for training and test subsets. In Fig. 2a (BTE), both curves decrease rapidly within the early iterations and then approach a stable plateau, showing that additional trees provide diminishing returns beyond the converged region.

Figure 2: a) Learning curves-BTE; b) Parity plot-BTE (predicted versus actual)

Fig. 3a (NO_x) and Fig. 4a (HC) display the same convergence pattern, with the test curve remaining above the training curve but stabilizing without late-stage divergence, which is consistent with controlled generalization error rather than progressive overfitting.

Figure 3: a) Learning curves-NO_x; b) Parity plot-NO_x (predicted versus actual)

Figure 4: a) Learning curves-HC; b) Parity plot-HC (predicted versus actual)

Figures 2b, 3b, and 4b present parity plots for the held-out test set, where the dashed 45° line denotes perfect agreement between measured and predicted values. In Fig. 2b (BTE), the points cluster closely around the reference line, consistent with the reported test accuracy ($R^2 = 0.9771$), indicating that the surrogate reproduces the observed BTE trend over the tested domain. Fig. 3b (NO_x) shows similarly tight alignment with the reference line ($R^2 = 0.9795$), with only small departures at the upper end of the NO_x range. Fig. 4b (HC) exhibits the strongest agreement ($R^2 = 0.9901$), where the scatter remains narrow across the full HC range, supporting the use of the HC surrogate for subsequent optimization.

3.3 Gain-based importance from the trained surrogates

To examine how the trained models allocate explanatory weight across the six input features, XGBoost gain-based importance values were extracted from each fitted model using the built-in feature_importance output. The resulting importance distributions for BTE, NO_x, and HC are provided in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Relative feature importance obtained from XGBoost gain for each response model.

3.4 Point optimization using RSM desirability

A desirability-based optimum was obtained using the response surface models developed in Design-Expert. The desirability formulation specified maximization of BTE and minimization of NO_x and HC, while constraining all input factors to remain within their experimentally tested bounds. The resulting best solution, including the predicted responses at the optimum operating point and the overall desirability value, is reported in Table 6.

Table 6: RSM desirability optimum and predicted responses

Parameter	Value
Octane (RON)	91.12
Solketal (% v/v)	9.88
Load (W)	1796.77

3.5 Comparison of RSM desirability optimum and NSGA-III compromise

The RSM desirability solution and the NSGA-III compromise solution yield different operating settings and predicted responses, reflecting the distinct optimization criteria used by each approach. RSM returns a single point optimum based on desirability aggregation, whereas NSGA-III identifies a compromise from a Pareto set using ASF weighting. The two resulting solutions are presented side-by-side in Table 7 to enable direct comparison of decision variables and predicted outcomes.

Table 7: Side-by-side comparison of the RSM desirability optimum and NSGA-III compromise solution

Metric	RSM desirability optimum	NSGA-III compromise	% Difference (NSGA vs RSM)
Load (W)	1796.77	1627.86	-9.40%
Solketal (% v/v)	9.88	8.19	-17.17%

Metric	RSM desirability optimum	NSGA-III compromise	% Difference (NSGA vs RSM)
Octane (RON)	91.12	88.05	-3.37%

The RSM desirability optimum and the NSGA-III compromise do not coincide because they arise from different optimization formulations. The desirability method reduces multiple responses to a single composite objective through user-defined desirability functions and weights, yielding one best point under that scalar aggregation. In contrast, NSGA-III explores the multi-objective trade-space directly and returns a set of non-dominated solutions; the reported compromise point is then selected using an achievement scalarization function (ASF), reflecting preference-based balancing rather than a single aggregated desirability. Consequently, deviations in the decision variables (Table 7) are expected and indicate genuine trade-offs among BTE, NO_x, and HC within the modeled domain.

3.6 NSGA-III Pareto search under feasibility constraints

Multi-objective optimization was carried out using NSGA-III with the objective vector formulated for minimization as $[-BTE, NO_x, HC]$. Brake thermal efficiency was negated to represent efficiency maximization within the minimization-based genetic search. The feasible search space was restricted using the convex hull and trust-region constraints defined in the Methods section to ensure that candidate solutions remained within data-supported regions. From the resulting Pareto set, a single compromise operating point was identified using an achievement scalarizing function with weights, thereby assigning same priority to all three objectives during compromise selection. The selected compromise solution is reported in Table 8.

Table 8: NSGA-III compromise solution selected using ASF weights

Parameter	Value
Load (W)	1627.86
Solketal (% v/v)	8.19
Octane (RON)	88.05
Predicted BTE (%)	12.16
Predicted NO _x (ppm)	19.64
Predicted HC (ppm)	166.94

Figure 6 summarizes the trade-offs among the three objectives in pairwise form. In the NO_x–BTE plane (left), the operating points indicate that higher BTE is generally associated with higher NO_x, highlighting the efficiency–NO_x conflict that motivates multi-objective selection. The selected compromise point (red marker) lies at lower BTE than the gasoline baseline (blue marker) but achieves a modest reduction in NO_x.

In the HC–BTE plane (middle) and HC–NO_x plane (right), the compromise point shows a clear reduction in HC relative to the baseline, with the HC shift being substantially larger than the accompanying NO_x shift. Collectively, the markers indicate that the chosen compromise

prioritizes HC reduction and slight NO_x improvement at the cost of reduced BTE, consistent with a constrained Pareto trade-off within the experimentally supported domain.

Fig. 6. Pareto visualizations from NSGA-III.

3.7 Matched-condition baseline comparison for the selected NSGA-III compromise

To quantify the influence of solketal at the selected NSGA-III compromise operating point, a matched-condition gasoline baseline was defined by setting solketal to 0% while keeping load and octane fixed at the compromise values. Baseline responses were then evaluated using the same trained surrogate models to ensure that the comparison reflects only the change in solketal fraction. The baseline and compromise predictions, together with absolute and percent differences, are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9: Baseline (0% solketal) versus NSGA-III compromise at matched load and octane

Case	Load (W)	Octane (RON)	Solketal (% v/v)	BTE (%)	NO _x (ppm)	HC (ppm)
Baseline (0% Solketal)	1627.86	88.05	0.00	15.04	20.59	200.27
NSGA-II	1627.86	88.05	8.19	12.16	19.64	166.94
Change (NSGA-III – Baseline)	–	–	+8.19	–2.89 (–19.2%)	–0.94 (–4.6%)	–33.33 (–16.6%)

4 Conclusions

This study developed and demonstrated a data-constrained, multi-objective optimization workflow for spark-ignition operation using solketal–gasoline blends under electrically loaded generator conditions. A 90-point experimental matrix spanning load, solketal fraction, and gasoline octane was used to train high-accuracy XGBoost surrogate models for BTE, NO_x, and HC, enabling rapid

evaluation of candidate operating points without extrapolating beyond the tested domain. The surrogate models reproduced the experimental response behavior with strong test-set agreement, supporting their use as computational proxies for subsequent optimization.

Response surface modeling provided an interpretable representation of the factor effects and confirmed the expected response conflicts, particularly between efficiency and NO_x across the operating plane. Multi-objective optimization using NSGA-III was then executed under explicit feasibility region controls. The convex hull constraint limited the search to the envelope of observed experiments, and the trust-region constraint restricted candidates to proximity neighborhoods where surrogate predictions remain reliable. This constraint formulation is the central methodological contribution, as it prevents algorithmic exploration into data-sparse regions that can produce numerically attractive but physically ungrounded recommendations.

A compromise solution selected from the constrained Pareto set reduced HC by 16.6% and NO_x by 4.6% relative to the matched gasoline-only baseline at identical load and octane, while shifting the operating point away from the high-efficiency region. The pairwise trade-off visualization confirms that the selected point lies within the interior of the feasible cloud rather than at an extreme endpoint, indicating a balanced emissions-oriented compromise under the imposed validity controls.

The outcomes support Sustainable Development Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) by advancing an optimization framework that improves the environmental performance of practical spark-ignition power units using a glycerol-derived oxygenate, and SDG 13 (Climate Action) by demonstrating measurable reductions in regulated exhaust species under data-bounded operating recommendations. More broadly, the proposed constrained surrogate-based workflow provides a transferable template for sustainable fuel screening and operating-point selection when experimental budgets are limited and model extrapolation risk must be explicitly controlled.

Future work should extend the present workflow beyond the current three-response formulation and single-platform dataset by incorporating additional regulated and performance-relevant metrics (e.g., CO, CO₂, particulate proxies, and combustion stability indicators) and, where possible, sustainability-oriented measures that better capture environmental trade-offs across the operating map. Equally important is targeted experimental confirmation: a small, strategically chosen set of validation tests around the selected compromise and the Pareto knee should be conducted to verify surrogate predictions, quantify predictive uncertainty, and enable iterative model recalibration within the same data-bounded regime. Finally, the optimization layer can be strengthened by adopting uncertainty-aware or robust multi-objective selection and sequential design (active learning) to prioritize the most informative next experiments, thereby improving the reliability and transferability of the constrained surrogate-based decision support tool to other oxygenates, engines, and operating envelopes.

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